

THE USE OF RESOURCES IN THE PROVISION OF INFORMATION.

Dadakhan Raimbayev

Karakalpak State University

Karakalpak philology and journalism

student of the 4th stage of the faculty

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Annotation: this article is written in online journalism about the appearance, structure of sites and the provision of information on them.

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The Internet is a huge treasure of unconditional Information in which millions of people leave information, and millions more share it with them. The task of journalists is to be able to find the necessary information from this huge ocean of information. In many cases, this is no different from the usual processes, such as historical archives, etc., through telephone interactions, from the process of working with resources that journalists always carry out. But some of the sources of information like this are old today. The Internet today serves as a source of information not only for higher reporters, but also for journalists of print television radio of various media representatives. Today, among the daily tasks of each editorial office, the verification of facts by going to the internet finding additional information for certain information is in the process of finding digital information that serves to enrich them. For internet journalists, internet resources are considered an important link. Because it is the sources themselves that become part of the material. Future journalists provide their readers with hyperlinks to sources and, in turn, provide them with the opportunity to get to know the information more widely. It can complement that good journalists always cite quotes from sources that give journalists information that can provide readers themselves with opportunities to familiarize themselves with these resources. It is this feature that is considered their feature that distinguishes journalism from other traditional types of journalistic activities. This is not information related to the initial qualification of the reporter but rather will be skills aimed at improving the skills of the online sealer. Here, speaking about computer-based journalistic activities, it is necessary to stop at effective methods of working with information sources that serve to enrich the material, and first study the specifics of email and forums as journalistic sources of information. After that, it is envisaged to achieve success in covering information by sorting and classifying information sources on the internet. The internet as a source of information for a reporter may appear in the process of obtaining information from the internet as a journalist's search for information

by phone. In it, too, it is in this that the reporter, knowing the phone number to determine to whom to contact the understanding of what to ask the question, must know in what way the information obtained will be used in his material, and the search for information on the internet begins in the same way as finding information from other sources. The most important question is that in the process I need information who has this source of information may or may not be online. To say that the Internet replaces the usual sources of information, to some extent it provides new ways of working with sources of information sometimes even information that is difficult to find from sources can be obtained more widely from traditional sources of information. In order to effectively use the electronic service of the Information Agency MCHBQ.com separate paragraph it is in paragraph dedicated to the use of the internet that recommendations from real professional life are presented. For example take it very seriously when it comes to accuracy internet is not an authority it's just a tool be sure of its accuracy before relying on the source from it. You may have been given a number of internet sites and email addresses never give him a referral without identifying them. Always check them first only then it is said that it is appropriate that you trace the material. Along with the fact that the Internet is a fast media in terms of information distribution, a non-false factual format can also serve as a quick service for the dissemination of information. For example, on one of the American humorist sites, the name of a feature film is ridiculous and untrue, even without the help of a translated system declared it. After that, errors from the material that spread this message also came out on the radio air thus the information continued to spread widely without stopping. Journalistic sites from past experience it can be said that reprint it is not yet journalistic to convey information while always sitting in the same place forming information based on other knowledge and covering it it is just a technique that the editorial itself must verify this information before printing it so as not to fall into that false information circle.

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